

Reproduction Study of "Post Processing Recommender Systems with Knowledge Graphs for Recency, Popularity, and Diversity of Explanations"

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This work attempts to reproduce the results obtained in "Post Processing Recommender Systems with Knowledge Graphs for Recency, Popularity, and Diversity of Explanations". We were able to run the authors' provided code but were unable to replicate the numerical results mentioned in the paper, and found some inconsistencies between the described and actual behaviour.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproducibility, Recommender Systems, Experimental Design, Explainability, Knowledge Graphs

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1 Introduction

This report seeks to reproduce the results described in the paper titled "Post Processing Recommender Systems with Knowledge Graphs for Recency, Popularity, and Diversity of Explanations" [Balloccu et al. 2022]. The authors sought to improve the quality of explanations provided to users as to why items were recommended while preserving overall recommendation utility. They conceptualized three properties to describe the quality of explanations: linking interaction recency (LIR), shared entity popularity (SEP), and explanation type diversity (ETD). They then proposed a re-ranking approach that optimizes these properties to generate the top- k list of recommended items.

The re-ranking approach extends a method called policy-guided path reasoning (PGPR). PGPR uses reinforcement learning to optimize a recommendation model while searching for paths in a knowledge graph, which form the basis for explanations. The authors use the three properties and normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG) as metrics to compare between different re-ranking configurations, as well as with baseline models; NDCG represents overall recommendation utility. The paper's methodology was applied to two public datasets: MovieLens-1M (ML1M) and LastFM-1B (LASTFM) [Harper and Konstan 2015; Schedl 2016a].

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2 Experimental Setup

The authors' source code and data can be found in <https://github.com/giacobalocco/explanation-quality-recsys>. The code is written in Python and a list of required libraries and detailed instructions are provided. The GitHub repository also includes a link to the pre-processed datasets and the original datasets that were used.

Our approach was to execute the unmodified code using Python 3.7.1 with the configurations described in the paper. To elaborate, the authors reported only the top-10 recommended lists and used a weighted optimization re-ranking instead of soft optimization. The results were then compared to those reported on the paper. We also executed the code across a variety of platforms to verify consistency of results in different environments.

However, in the paper, the authors specify that they use only the top 10 recommended items in a list for consistency's sake. However, there exist two versions of obtaining them in the provided code: The `-agent_topk` variable is one of 25-50-1, 10-12-1, where 25-50-1 represents 25 recommendations being made, but the top 10 of those being chosen. In the paper, it is not clearly stated which one is used.

We tried to reproduce the results from the original paper on different devices, using various versions of AMD and Intel CPUs, and running Windows 10 and Windows 11, Mac OS 15.2, and Fedora 41 operating systems. On the linux system, issues with a library and the xwayland system caused the need for some debugging but had no effect on the end results.

Although our results were the same across all devices, they were different from those in the paper, probably due to data preprocessing discrepancies. From this, we can conclude that the operating system and CPU have no influence on the results.

2.1 Good aspects about the paper's reproducibility

- (1) A GitHub Repository with the full code, hyperparameters, as well as both raw and preprocessed data was available. The raw LASTFM data becoming unavailable due to licensing issues is not the fault of the authors.
- (2) The repository also lists all required libraries as well as their versions
- (3) The experimental setup is well-explained, including the order of the data as well as the train-test split.

2.2 Issues Affecting Reproducibility

The GitHub repository simply states that the code will run with Python version 3.6 or higher. However, version 3.6, along with higher versions such as 3.13.0 or 3.9.6, are incompatible with the required libraries. Version 3.7.1 was found to be compatible.

The original LASTFM dataset is no longer publicly available due to licensing issues [*LFM-1b Dataset*; *LFM-1b UGP Dataset* n.d.]. The authors do provide the unmodified dataset that they used. However, they seemingly took a subset of the original dataset; the original dataset has approximately 120,000 users listed, while an analysis of the authors' unmodified dataset shows only 16,000 users [Schedl 2016b]. It is unclear how this subset was created.

An inspection of the source code revealed three discrepancies in the code's data preprocessing compared to what was described in the paper:

- (1) Users in the two datasets that do not list gender, age, and timestamps of interactions with items are supposed to be dropped. However, the code does not remove users that have no gender or age.
- (2) Films and songs that are not present in the knowledge graph as entities or have less than 200 interactions should be removed. However, this check does not exist in the code.

- (3) The dataset should be ordered chronologically and split into 70% training, 10% validation, and 20% test. This is done for the knowledge graphs of the M1LM dataset, however the LASTFM dataset uses an 80% training and 20% test split without validation. This 80-20% split is also applied on the dataset mapper function for both datasets.

3 Results

Table 1 shows the differences between the preprocessed dataset’s statistics as reported by the paper, and the statistics of the reproduced preprocessed dataset. The table indicates that the authors applied filtering rules to the users and products (films and songs) that are inconsistent with what they described in the paper.

Table 1. Comparison of the preprocessed dataset statistics between the paper and ours.

	ML1M			LASTFM		
	Unprocessed	Paper	Reproduced	Unprocessed	Paper	Reproduced
Users	6040	6040	6040	15.773	15.773	12.699
Products	3883	3226	3043	47.982	47.981	7786
Interactions	1.000.161	1.000.209	995.444	21.946.833	3.955.598	20.601.244

(a) Results from the original paper

(b) Our experimental results

Fig. 1. Gain/loss of re-ranking approaches (R-PGPR, P-PGPR, D-PGPR) compared to the original model in terms of NDCG, LIR, SEP, and ETD, with varying α in $[0.1, 0.5]$ on ML1M (left) and LASTFM (right).

Figure 1 displays the gain/loss in recommendation utility and explainability compared to the original PGPR model when optimizing one of the three properties. R-PGPR optimizes LIR, P-PGPR maximizes SEP, and D-PGPR optimizes ETD. The exact numbers of the reproduced results differs from the original results, but they do show similar trends to the ones in the paper. For example, the ETD for R-PGPR for the ML1M dataset is decreasing with increasing alpha values.

Table 2. Recommendation utility (NDCG).

Baseline			Ours		
Model	ML1M	LASTFM	Model	ML1M	LASTFM
FM	0.32	0.15	R-PGPR	0.34	0.14
BPR	0.33	0.13	P-PGPR	0.33	0.13
NMF	0.32	0.14	D-PGPR	0.32	0.14
CKE	0.33	0.14	DP-PGPR	0.31	0.13
CFKG	0.27	0.08	PR-PGPR	0.32	0.13
KGAT	0.33	0.15	DR-PGPR	0.32	0.13
PGPR	0.33	0.14	DPR-PGPR	0.31	0.13

(a) Results from the original paper

Model	ML1M	LASTFM
R-PGPR	0.32	0.12
P-PGPR	0.39	0.12
D-PGPR	0.32	0.12
DP-PGPR	0.31	0.11
PR-PGPR	0.32	0.12
DR-PGPR	0.32	0.11
DPR-PGPR	0.31	0.11

(b) Our experimental results

Table 2 is a reproduction of Table 3 in the original paper. The authors did not specify what alpha values they used to produce these results. For our results, we chose $\alpha = 0.1$ as this value of α produces higher NDCG values. Our results are similar for the ML1M dataset but differ for the LASTFM dataset.

In Table 3, the authors show how optimizing combinations of the three properties affects the metrics for quality of explanation. Our reproduced results are listed in Table 4. Again, our results are obtained using $\alpha = 0.1$, as this value of α maximizes the metrics. However, while our results follow a similar trend, they do not exactly match those reported in the paper.

Table 3. Explanation Quality (EQ, LIR, EP, ETD). Results from the original paper.

	ML1M				LASTFM			
	EQ \uparrow	LIR \uparrow	SEP \uparrow	ETD \uparrow	EQ \uparrow	LIR \uparrow	SEP \uparrow	ETD \uparrow
PGPR	0.81	0.43	0.26	0.12	1.07	0.56	0.38	0.13
R-PGPR	1.37	0.88	0.37	0.12	1.50	0.93	0.43	0.14
P-PGPR	1.22	0.44	0.63	0.15	1.42	0.55	0.67	0.20
D-PGPR	1.05	0.43	0.33	0.29	1.50	0.55	0.47	0.48
DP-PGPR	1.37	0.44	0.70	0.22	1.56	0.55	<u>0.68</u>	0.32
PR-PGPR	1.71	<u>0.86</u>	0.70	0.14	<u>1.80</u>	<u>0.86</u>	0.50	0.43
DR-PGPR	1.59	0.84	0.46	0.29	2.01	<u>0.86</u>	0.69	<u>0.46</u>
DPR-PGPR	<u>1.70</u>	0.79	<u>0.67</u>	<u>0.23</u>	1.76	0.83	0.63	0.29

For each metric: best result in **bold**, second-best result underlined.

Table 4. Explanation Quality (EQ, LIR, EP, ETD). Our experimental results.

Model	EQ	LIR	SEP	ETD
PGPR	0.78	0.16	0.46	0.15
R-PGPR	1.01	0.34	0.53	0.15
P-PGPR	1.17	0.16	0.82	0.20
D-PGPR	1.02	0.15	0.60	0.27
DP-PGPR	1.24	0.15	<u>0.80</u>	0.29
PR-PGPR	<u>1.26</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.74	0.18
DR-PGPR	1.20	<u>0.33</u>	0.58	<u>0.28</u>
DPR-PGPR	1.31	0.32	0.74	0.25

(a) Results for ML1M dataset

Model	EQ	LIR	SEP	ETD
PGPR	1.00	0.08	0.79	0.13
R-PGPR	1.03	0.16	0.74	0.13
P-PGPR	1.11	0.09	0.86	<u>0.16</u>
D-PGPR	1.00	0.08	0.74	0.18
DP-PGPR	1.12	0.08	<u>0.85</u>	0.18
PR-PGPR	1.15	<u>0.15</u>	0.84	0.15
DR-PGPR	1.08	<u>0.15</u>	0.75	0.18
DPR-PGPR	<u>1.14</u>	0.15	0.83	<u>0.16</u>

(b) Results for LASTFM dataset

 Table 5. Performance comparison of models with respect to Δ NDCCG, Δ LIR, Δ SEP, and Δ ETD on the ML1M and LASTFM datasets. Results from the original paper.

	ML1M				LASTFM			
	Δ NDCCG \downarrow	Δ LIR \downarrow	Δ SEP \downarrow	Δ ETD \downarrow	Δ NDCCG \downarrow	Δ LIR \downarrow	Δ SEP \downarrow	Δ ETD \downarrow
PGPR	0.034*	-0.011	0.015*	0.002	-0.001	-0.014*	0.019*	0.002*
R-PGPR	0.033*	-0.007	0.008	0.002	-0.002	-0.008*	0.025*	0.003*
P-PGPR	0.036*	-0.013*	-0.001	0.002	-0.001	-0.004	0.017*	0.001
D-PGPR	0.034*	-0.014*	0.006	-0.011*	0.009*	-0.010*	0.013*	-0.015*
DP-PGPR	0.048*	-0.011*	-0.014*	-0.010*	0.006*	-0.003	0.020*	-0.006*
PR-PGPR	0.034*	-0.006	-0.009	0.002	-0.003	-0.008*	0.020*	-0.004*
DR-PGPR	0.036*	-0.012*	0.002	-0.008*	0.006	-0.004*	0.022*	-0.010*
DPR-PGPR	0.041*	-0.006	-0.009*	-0.005	0.005	-0.006*	0.024*	-0.004

(*) Statistically significant difference under a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test, $p = 0.05$.

The authors use the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test to determine statistical significance between the baseline and re-ranked PGPR models in Table 5. This test is typically designed to for comparing more than two groups. However, the authors compare only two groups, male vs female. In this case, a more appropriate test would be the Mann-Whitney U test .

Table 6. Our experimental results, with asterisks signifying statistical significance of $p > 0.05$ under a Kruskal-Wallis test

Model	Δ NDCG ML1M	Δ LIR ML1M	Δ SEP ML1M	Δ ETD ML1M	Δ NDCG LASTFM	Δ LIR LASTFM	Δ SEP LASTFM	Δ ETD LASTFM
PGPR	-0.000151	-0.006645*	0.000699	0.005592	-0.001471	-0.002974*	-0.000558	0.000922
R-PGPR	-0.000817	-0.028189*	-0.007524	-0.002680	-0.001400	-0.012808*	-0.002032	-0.000703*
P-PGPR	-0.000919	-0.010209	0.000340	-0.001132	-0.007479*	-0.000484	-0.002534	-0.000540
D-PGPR	0.000335	-0.016335*	0.003755	0.005089	-0.000518*	-0.004115*	0.000153	0.005838
DP-PGPR	0.002593	-0.017050*	0.000800	0.006629	-0.001269	-0.005801	0.000469	-0.000581
PR-PGPR	0.000456	-0.027717*	0.002253	-0.002199	-0.000382	-0.012518*	-0.000957	-0.003093
DR-PGPR	-0.000683	-0.027897*	-0.002666	0.001099	-0.000820	-0.012580*	-0.002251	0.003734
DPR-PGPR	-0.000143	-0.028008*	0.001906	0.007367	-0.000936	-0.012304*	-0.000353	-0.000645

4 Conclusion

In this experiment, we attempted to replicate the results from the paper “Post Processing Recommender Systems with Knowledge Graphs for Recency, Popularity, and Diversity of Explanations.” The paper proposes a recommender system (RS), which combines direct connections between users and items with factors like how recent an interaction is, how popular an entity is, and the variety of explanations provided. Although the overall approach was well-defined, we were unable to replicate the exact results, primarily due to discrepancies in the data preprocessing steps. Despite these challenges, the experiment provides insights into potential improvements for the code and dataset preparation processes. Resolving these issues will be crucial for ensuring accurate replication in future experiments.

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